

Evaluation of granular insecticides to control rice root weevil

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In a trial in farmers' fields in Patiala district during the 1979 wet season, eight granular and one emulsifiable concentrate insecticides were evaluated for control of rice root weevil *Echinocnemus oryzae*. The randomized block design used a 33-m² plot size. Granular insecticides were broadcast in paddy water. The emulsifiable concentrate was diluted and sprinkled. Larval populations were counted by uprooting 10 hills/plot immediately before and 10 and 20 days

Effect of granular insecticides on control of rice root weevil, Punjab, India, 1979 wet season.

Insecticide ^a	Larval population reduction ^b (%)	
	10 DAT	20 DAT
Aldrin (Aldrin 30EC)	66.9 ab	84.5 ab
Carbofuran (Furadan 3G)	71.8 a	89.6 a
Disulfoton (Solvirex 5G)	56.6 bc	65.0 c
Fensulfthion (Dasanit 5G)	64.0 abc	63.6 c
Gamma BHC (Lindane 6G)	52.6 a	62.2 c
Isofenphos (Oftanol 5G)	57.0 bc	76.6 ab
Mephosfolan (Cytrolane 5G)	77.3 a	88.4 ab
Phorate (Thimet 10G)	75.6 a	81.2 ab
Quinalphos (Ekalux 5G)	73.8 a	84.9 ab

^aApplied @ 0.75 kg a.i./ha 21 days after transplanting. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. DAT = days after treatment.

after treatment (DAT).

At 10 DAT, none of the insecticides had caused more than 80% reduction in larval population (see table). However, carbofuran, mephosfolan, phorate, and quinalphos caused more than 70%

reduction.

At 20 DAT, aldrin, carbofuran, mephosfolan, phorate, and quinalphos had caused more than 80% reduction in larval populations. Isofenphos caused more than 70% reduction. ■

Effect of carbofuran root zone application rate on feeding activity and mortality of the green leafhopper

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Tungro, a serious rice disease, is controlled by planting resistant varieties and by applying insecticides. Incorporating carbofuran in the root zone at planting time generally controls tungro by preventing green leafhopper (*Nephotettix virescens*) feeding. An insectary study was conducted to determine the effect of carbofuran rates on residual activity and feeding of the insect.

Three rates of encapsulated carbofuran 3% granules were inserted into the root zone. Beginning 1 day after application, 10 adult female green leafhoppers were caged over filter paper on the plants at 5-day intervals. Forty-eight hours after infestation, insect mortality was recorded. Feeding activity was determined by measuring the size of purple-stained spots produced by the action of honeydew and ninhydrin on filter papers treated with 0.01% ninhydrin solution.

Although there was substantial feeding at all rates, less feeding activity occurred at the rates of 0.75 and 0.50 kg a.i./ha than in the control until 40 days after treatment (see table). It was observed that the insects kept moving

Residual activity of carbofuran applied in the root zone to control green leafhopper and its effect on insect feeding.^a IRR I insectary, 1980.

Days after treatment	0.75 kg a.i./ha	0.50 kg a.i./ha	0.25 kg a.i./ha	Control
	<i>Insect mortality (%)</i>			
1	90 a	33 b	38 b	0 c
5	100 a	98 a	63 b	0 c
10	100 a	100 a	100 a	0 b
15	100 a	100 a	78 b	0 c
20	95 a	98 a	70 b	0 c
25	90 a	50 b	20 b	0 c
30	80 a	48 b	13 c	0 c
35	68 a	40 b	10 c	3 c
40	65 a	25 b	3 c	3 c
45	30 a	5 ab	0 b	0 b
	<i>Feeding activity (mm²)</i>			
1	106 b	172 b	262 b	625 a
5	60 b	91 b	205 b	540 a
10	44 b	46 b	52 b	623 a
15	34 b	37 b	136 b	626 a
20	46 b	60 b	117 b	637 a
25	115 c	349 c	736 b	978 a
30	173 b	256 b	593 a	669 a
35	177 b	338 b	652 a	641 a
40	210 b	394 b	733 a	641 a
45	438 b	874 a	1079 a	904 a

^aIn a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

away from the treated plants, suggesting that the feeding that occurred was limited to a short time. Under field con-

ditions, feeding time on treated plants may be too short to inoculate plants with tungro virus. ■

Fluctuation of yellow stem borer moths in Tirur, India

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The yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*, a major pest of rice in Chingleput

district of Tamil Nadu, occurs in all three seasons: sornavari (Apr-May to Aug-Sep), samba (Jul-Aug to Nov-Dec), and navarai (Dec-Jan to Apr-May).

Light trap studies were conducted from January 1976 to December 1979 to study the pattern of stem borer occurrence and to find the peak periods of